

CRACKING AND DAMAGE MECHANISMS IN NITRIDED Ti64 GRADE 5 ALLOY AFTER HIGH CYCLE FATIGUE

S. Stekovic¹, R. Boyd² & L. Selegård³

The aim of this study is to evaluate the effect of two nitriding heat treatments on high cycle fatigue of Ti64 (Grade 5) alloy. For this, axial fatigue tests have been performed on untreated and nitrided round bar specimens under constant amplitude load-controlled mode at a frequency of 20 Hz at room temperature and in laboratory air. After the testing, the fractured surfaces and microstructures were investigated by scanning electron microscopy, focused ion beam, transmission electron microscopy and scanning transmission electron microscopy. Cross-sectional studies show that two different layers were formed after the nitriding processes, namely, a top compound layer and a diffusion layer below it. Additionally, a very thin layer rich in aluminium was also detected. The fatigue results show that the nitriding treatments are detrimental to the fatigue life when compared to the untreated and extruded Ti64 alloy. The main conclusion is that the reduction of high cycle fatigue life is a result of the cracking of the nitrided layers.

Keywords: crack initiation, fatigue, microstructure, nitriding

INTRODUCTION

Ti-6Al-4V (Ti64) is a dual-phase titanium alloy consisting of α (alpha) and β (beta) phases having hexagonal close-packed (HCP) and body centered cubic (BCC) crystal structures, respectively. It is widely used in the aerospace and aircraft industry due to its high strength to weight ratio. However, its utilisation for certain aircraft components, such as hinges, has been limited due to its relatively low hardness and poor wear resistance. This affects the durability and performance of these components, especially in demanding environments where high mechanical stresses are common. Various methods such as nitriding, carburising, plating and others are used to improve these properties. Nitriding is a thermo-chemical process involving the diffusion of nitrogen (N) into the surface of metals to enhance hardness, wear and corrosion resistance, as well as fatigue strength of metal components, Zhang et al. [1]. Following nitriding, a compound layer and an underlying diffusion zone are often formed near the surface. In the case of Ti64, the compound layer primarily consists of titanium nitrides such as TiN and Ti₂N, while the diffusion zone consists of an interstitial solid solution of nitrogen dissolved within the alloy, Perez [2]. Unlike traditional coatings, the compound layer is integrally grown into the underlying Ti64 substrate.

¹ Engineering Materials, Department of Management and Engineering, Linköping University, Linköping, Sweden

² Plasma and Coatings Physics, Department of Physics, Chemistry and Biology, Linköping University, Linköping, Sweden

³ Saab Aeronautics AB, Linköping, Sweden

Nitriding is very relevant today as it presents a potential alternative to hard chromium plating that has been the standard industrial process for improving wear and corrosion protection in aerospace applications. Hard chromium plating typically contains hexavalent chromium (Cr^{6+}), known to be carcinogenic and toxic and subject to stringent regulations of the European Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation, and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH), [3]. Hence, there is an urgent need to find safer alternatives with comparable or superior properties and functionalities. While several commercial alternatives exist, such as high velocity oxygen fuel spraying and various physical and chemical vapor deposition processes, Kubinski et al. [4] and Bryskin et al. [5], none can fully substitute hard chromium on their own due to performance issues related to e.g. fatigue, Zhu et al. [6]. Nitriding emerges as a highly promising alternative due to its environmental sustainability and potential high number of applications.

Only a small number of studies have reported the impact of nitriding on titanium alloys, particularly concerning fatigue properties. Gas nitriding has a reported varying effect on the fatigue behaviour of titanium alloys. For Ti-6Al-4V, the overall fatigue (rotating bending) strength seems to be reduced by gas nitriding compared to annealed or untreated specimens (Tokaji et al. [7]). However, the fatigue limit was slightly increased for certain nitrided specimens, indicating a complex relationship between nitriding and fatigue behavior. Premature crack initiation was observed at the nitrided specimens leading to a decrease in crack initiation resistance compared to annealed specimens. In addition, faster crack growth rates were observed in the nitrided specimens. De Castro et al. [8] reported that plasma nitriding led to an increase in low cycle fatigue strength, while high cycle fatigue (rotating bending) behaviour remained similar between the treated and untreated conditions for Ti64. The thickness of the diffusion layer was irregular and microcracks seemed to occur at the interface between the α and β phases. The fatigue strength (rotating bending) of Ti64 ion-nitrided specimens was lower compared to non-ion-nitrided specimens in Nishida and Hattori [9], however, when compared to annealed specimens under the same temperature conditions, the fatigue strength of ion-nitrided specimens was superior. It seemed that the presence of the chemical compound surface layer negatively impacted the fatigue strength of the nitrided specimen. The study of Raveh et al. [10] examined fatigue crack propagation rate (FCPR) and particularly threshold stress intensity factor (K_{th}) values for plasma nitrided Ti64 to understand crack tip shielding and resistance to crack growth. The FCPR curve analysis revealed that near threshold values were lower for the plasma nitriding specimens compared to untreated specimens. It was also stated in [10] that higher microhardness in the nitrided layer corresponded to a lower number of cycles for crack initiation. Gas blow induction-heating (GBIH) nitriding has a negative impact on the fatigue properties of Ti64 under axial loading conditions, Takesue et al. [11], due to grain coarsening and formation of a brittle compound layer. An intriguing finding from [11] suggests an improvement in the fatigue strength with the presence of a nitrogen diffusion layer in the absence of any compound layer formation.

Consequently, the objective of the present research has been to investigate mechanical performance of Ti64 subjected to two novel nitriding processes. The assessment involved a comparative analysis between nitrided Ti64 and untreated Ti64 by using hardness indentations, sliding pin-on-disc wear and tensile tests, as detailed and presented in Stekovic et al. [12, 13]. Additionally, fatigue tests were also performed, the results of which are detailed in this paper. Furthermore, the study also investigated surface roughness and residual stresses, for which several disc specimens were prepared. Following the test procedure, thorough fractographic and metallographic analyses were performed utilising light and electron microscopy.

MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Material

A commercially available annealed Ti64 alloy Grade 5 in form of round bars composed of ASTM 4928W alloy were utilised for mechanical testing and microstructural analysis in the study. The chemical composition is presented in Table 1. The bars were manufactured by Baoji First Titanium Industry Co., Ltd., China.

TABLE 1 Chemical composition of Ti64 bars (wt.%) according to the manufacture's specifications

Requirement	Fe	C	N	H	O	Y	Al	V	Ti	Residual	
	max 0.30	max 0.08	max 0.05	max 0.0125	max 0.20	max 0.005	5.5- 6.75	3.5- 4.5	Bal.	Each ≤ 0.10	Total ≤ 0.40
Analysis	0.17	0.021	0.017	<0.0006	0.168	<0.005	6.43	4.19	Bal.	<0.1	<0.4

The Ti64 material consists of two phases, a main hexagonal close-packed (HCP) α -phase and a second body-centered cubic (BCC) β -phase. Aluminium and vanadium were added to stabilise the α - and β -phase respectively. The properties of the $\alpha + \beta$ alloys can be controlled by heat treatment to produce a range of different mechanical properties, Pedersen [14] and Lütjering [15]. The maximum operating temperature is in the range of 315 to 400 °C, Boyer [16].

Specimen preparation

The specimens were prepared by machining round bars with a diameter of 19 mm as shown in Figure 1. The gauge length area of the specimens was ground to a surface finish of 0.2 μm . Nitriding was conducted in a vacuum furnace under ultra-pure N₂ gas atmosphere. Additionally, several discs, measuring 25.4 mm in diameter and 6 mm in thickness, were machined and subjected to nitriding processes for subsequent analysis for surface roughness, phase composition and residual stress depth profile. Surface roughness measurements were also conducted using a profilometer both before and after the nitriding processes.

FIGURE 1 Specimen design for axial high cycle fatigue tests.

Microstructure analysis

The surfaces and microstructures of the untreated and nitrided specimens were investigated by optical microscope Leica DM6 and scanning electron microscope (SEM) JSM-IT500 after the testing. The cross-sectional samples suitable for SEM and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) analysis were prepared by focused ion beam (FIB) using Zeiss EsB 1540 instrument. SEM analyses were done with Hitachi SU-70 equipped an energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS). Scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) analysis were performed using a FEI Tecnai G2 TF 20 UT microscope operated at 200 kV. The thickness of the nitrided layers were measured on polished cross-sections in the SEMs. The X-ray diffraction (XRD, XStress 3000G2R) was used to analyse the phases in the nitriding process.

Residual stress measurements

The residual stress measurements were carried out through the XRD (XStress 3000G2R) diffractometer equipped with a Cr X-ray tube with a wavelength of 0.0229 nm combined with material removal by etching. All measurements were performed on one position on each disc specimen. The measurements were carried out at 2 rotations (0° , 90°) measuring the diffraction peak at the (hkl) reflections for TiN phases with 0.02° scan step width. Optical microscopy method using confocal fusion was used to determine the electropolished depth.

Fatigue testing

Axial high cycle fatigue testing was undertaken on untreated and nitrided round bar specimens under constant amplitude load-controlled mode at a frequency of 20 Hz in laboratory air. The load ratio was $R=0.1$. All fatigue tests were performed using a servo hydraulic Instron 8000-072 fatigue test rig with ± 100 kN load cell and an Instron 8800 control system. All tests were carried out with sinusoidal waveform. The tests were stopped at 5×10^6 cycles if they did not fail earlier. For each load level, one specimen was tested. In total, 14 fatigue tests were conducted. Two tests with the untreated specimens were runouts and then re-tested at higher maximum stresses due to the limited availability of untreated specimens and to allow for further investigation of fracture behaviour. However, it is important to remember that the untreated specimens might have experienced damage accumulation at the lower stresses.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Microstructure characterisation

Both nitriding processes led to the formation of a compound layer on the top and a diffusion zone beneath it. A typical microstructure obtained after the nitriding processes of Ti64 specimens is presented in Figure 2a. Heterogeneities were observed in the cross-sections due to the variations in thickness within both the compound and diffusion layers. After the nitriding process 1, the average surface roughness measured $R_a = 0.554 \mu\text{m}$ with an average maximum height of the profile (depth) at $R_z = 5.480 \mu\text{m}$. After the nitriding process 2, the average surface roughness was $R_a = 0.242 \mu\text{m}$ with a depth of $R_z = 3.347 \mu\text{m}$. The as-machined surface has a roughness of $R_a = 0.1834 \mu\text{m}$ and $R_z = 1.1964 \mu\text{m}$. The compound layer had a thickness variation ranging between $0.9 \mu\text{m} - 1.69 \mu\text{m}$ for the nitriding process 1 while the thickness varied between $100-200 \text{ nm}$ in the nitriding process 2. Regarding the diffusion layer, the thickness varied between $0.8 \mu\text{m}$ and $2.5 \mu\text{m}$ in the nitriding process 1, while it was between $1 \mu\text{m}$ and $2 \mu\text{m}$ in the nitriding process 2. In the base Ti64-material,

β -phase (the bright phase) was observed in the grain boundaries. Highly concentrated nitrogen was observed in the compound layer while the diffusion layer was enriched in aluminium, Stekovic et al. [7]. The β -phase was not observed in the compound and diffusion layers. It seems that nitrogen diffusion shifts the β -phase transformation towards higher temperatures and increases the volume fraction of α -phase as shown by Edrisy and Farokhzadeh [17]. The oxygen signal was also strong at the surface of the sample while the titanium rich layer below it also contained nitrogen, the nitrogen signal being stronger than for the base material below it. It is worth mentioning that the nitrogen N-K α signal overlaps with the Ti-L α lines, which makes quantification difficult. The XRD pattern of the nitrated specimens demonstrated the presence of δ -TiN in the compound layers and a mix of ϵ -Ti₂N – Ti in the diffusion layers.

Residual stresses

The nitrated process 1 generated tensile stress at the surface for the diffraction plane (220) and compressive residual stress for the diffraction plane (301), Figure 2b. The stresses in the nitrated specimens decayed after 5 μ m, as determined by electro polishing, for both direction planes. The maximum tensile residual stress was measured to 150MPa for the (220) plane at 90 deg rotation while the highest compressive stress was similar for both rotations in the (301) plane with a value of about -230MPa. It seems that the rotation angle can significantly impact the measured residual stresses because different crystallographic orientations generate specific stress patterns due to anisotropy of the material. More precisely, the hexagonal close-packed (HCP) crystal structure contributes to anisotropic properties in Ti64 alloys. In addition, the orientation dependent distribution of residual stresses can be influenced by processing history, surface treatments, and microstructural features such as grain boundaries and texture.

FIGURE 2 Cross section of a microstructure (a) and residual stress profile (b) of a sample after the nitrating process 1.

Fatigue properties

Figure 3 shows the maximum stresses and the number of cycles to failure for the two nitriding processes and untreated Ti64 compared to the extruded data from the literature [18]. The stress and fatigue life values are not presented to protect the intellectual property rights. Nonetheless, certain trends can still be observed. Straight lines are included to facilitate the comparison of data points. Both nitrated processes show a reduction in high cycle fatigue life compared to both untreated and literature data. However, the second nitrated process demonstrates improved fatigue life under higher

maximum stresses compared to the first nitrided process. At two maximum stresses, two untreated specimens did not experience any failure until the tests were stopped at 5×10^6 cycles (run-out). When re-tested at higher stresses, significantly shorter finite lives were observed.

FIGURE 3 High cycle fatigue behaviour of two nitrided processes compared to the untreated specimens and extruded Ti64 from the literature in [18].

Fractography and crack initiation

The fractographic analysis of the fracture surfaces for the untreated specimens show some differences at different stress levels, Figure 4. The fatigue cracks initiated from surface in all tested specimens. At the highest maximum stress of 950MPa, a cup and cone fracture was observed, which is an indicator of ductile fracture in tension. A high magnification shows isolated voids and shallow dimples of varying size. At higher stresses, multiple crack initiation sites were observed. It is worth noting that the specimens tested at 950MPa and 900MPa were re-tested with the specimens from the fatigue tests conducted at lower stresses upon reaching the run-out limit.

Figure 5 shows the fracture surfaces of the specimens subjected to the nitriding process 1. At the stress level of 850MPa, a ductile cup and cone fracture with multiple initiation sites was observed. In contrast, at lower stresses, while several initiation sites were visible, the cup-and-cone feature was absent. The crack initiation occurred at the outer surface with a little crack growth at a stress of 750MPa. The nitrided layers can be from the underlying material at the lower applied maximum stresses. It appears that the cracks rapidly propagated along the nitrided layer and then extended further into the material's interior.

FIGURE 4 Fatigue fractured surfaces and initiation sites of the untreated specimens at different stress levels.

FIGURE 5 Fatigue fractured surfaces and initiation sites of the specimens nitrided with the process 1 at different stress levels.

A higher magnification SEM image of the specimen tested at 650MPa shows a small crack on the top of the nitrided layer, Figure 6. Near the surface, at the interdiffusion zone between the compound layer and the base material, signs of cleavage were observed as also seen in Figure 5 for the specimens tested at 750MPa.

FIGURE 6 SEM image of the fractured surface of the specimen tested at 650MPa with the nitrided process 1.

Figure 7 displays the fracture surfaces of the specimens subjected to the nitriding process 2. The fatigue cracks were found to originate from the surface under all applied stresses. A notable discrepancy in the fracture surface was noticed at a stress level of 850 MPa, where cracks initiated from both sides of the specimen circumference. In some cases, facets with smoother surface than the surrounding area were observed as shown in Figure 7 in the specimen tested at 750 MPa. Some facets are larger due to grain coarsening that probably occurred during the nitriding process, as found in the results from [19] after gas blow induction heating nitriding of Ti64. The nitrided layers are easily distinguishable from the underlying material, and transgranular brittle fractures within these layers are observable. The SEM analysis also reveals roundish defects on the surface of the nitrided layer as demonstrated in the specimen tested at 750 MPa.

FIGURE 7 Fatigue fractured surfaces and initiation sites of the specimens nitrided with the process 2 at different stress levels.

It is evident from Figure 3 that the nitriding processes negatively impacts the high cycle fatigue performance of Ti64. There are several potential reasons for the decrease in fatigue life. First, the higher elastic modulus of the compound layer compared to the substrate results in higher stresses at the surface during fatigue testing causing cracking. Second, grain coarsening of the α -phase may occur due to temperature increases above the β transus point for Ti64 as shown in [19]. Moreover, it was found in [20] that surface roughness increased after gas nitriding by formation of titanium nitrides and oxides on the surface. The average surface roughness and depth in the nitrided specimens were higher than the roughness and depth in the untreated specimens in this study. The higher surface roughness can increase stress concentration sites on surface causing early crack initiation. The residual stresses generated at the surface were about +150MPa in (220) and -230MPa in (301), which were reasonable low. Morital et al. [21] and Ongtrakulkij et al. [22] showed that significant compressive stresses were not generated after plasma nitriding in Ti64 as well. A slightly higher tensile residual stresses (265MPa at the surface) were measured in the laser gas nitrided Ti64 in [23]. Therefore, the residual stresses should not affect the fatigue life of the nitrided specimens.

In order to further examine possible reasons for the reduction in fatigue life, the fractured surfaces of the failed specimens were analysed with FIB-SEM, STEM and TEM. There were challenges encountered during the preparation of the samples due to geometry of the specimen, which complicated access to the electron and ion beams. A FIB section was obtained across a crack, positioned at the indicated location in Figures 8 corresponding to the nitriding process 1. Figure 8 reveals the crack internal structure and depth. It shows the transverse cracks below the surface. The higher magnification SEM images highlight width and internal features of the cracks that are shallow and wide. The lateral surface, shown on the top left low magnification image, consists of straight uniform parallel feed marks originating from the machining. There are also multiple cracks present on the lateral surface, propagating in a transgranular manner. The light grey wavy features containing black roundish details seen on the cross sections are cracks with voids.

FIGURE 8 Fatigue surface of Ti64 nitrided with the process 1 and FIB milled cross section of a crack corresponding to the location marked on the top left image. The specimen was tested at a maximum stress of 650MPa.

High-angle annular dark-field imaging (HAADF) and chemical mapping using energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) in STEM has shown that the diffusion layer is titanium and nitrogen rich but deficient in aluminium, Figure 9. Lack of aluminium in the compound layer indicates presence of the nitrides. The nitrogen signals are strong at the top of the crack in the diffusion layer. Cracks are observed propagating between the grains. The compound layer appears to have a 50 nm thick top layer.

FIGURE 9 Dark field and HAADF/EDSSTEMS images of the fatigued Ti64 specimen nitrided with the process 1. The specimen was tested at a maximum stress of 650MPa.

FIB cross sections have been taken from the specimen nitrided with the process 2 and tested at 800MPa, Figure 10. A platinum layer was deposited on the surface to protect its features from milling damage. Different features were observed on the surface of the specimen, i.e. machining feed marks and fatigue cracks. One FIB-section was taken from each feature, as shown on the top left hand side SEM image in Figure 10, to study crack initiation and evolution. The FIB cross-section of the machining feed mark exposed a thin long crack at the bottom of the groove. The FIB cross section examination of the surface fatigue crack revealed a wider transgranular fracture extending through the diffusion layer and penetrating deeply into the base material. As shown in Figure 10 on the right bottom hand side, a thin top layer covered the surface followed by a diffusion zone. There are also elongated features (marked with green circles) along the grains in the diffusion zone.

FIGURE 10 FIB milled cross sections and dark field TEM images of the fatigued surface of Ti64 nitrided with the process 2. The specimen was tested at a maximum stress of 800MPa.

Figure 11: A higher magnification SEM image of the crack initiated from the machining groove.

Upon closer examination at higher magnification, it was revealed that the elongated crack within the groove originated from the base of the machining groove, Figure 11. The crack originated at the surface of the compound layer and then propagated through both the diffusion layer and the base material. Furthermore, there is clear evidence of the crack deflecting along a grain boundary between the diffusion layer and the base material before continuing its transverse propagation into the base material.

EDS-STEM revealed an additional very thin (20nm) aluminium rich layer at the surface while the diffusion zone was aluminium deficient, Figure 12. Furthermore, the distribution of elements presented in Figure 12 shows a concentration of nitrogen and titanium below the aluminium rich layer indicating the zone containing nitrides.

FIGURE 12 EDS-STEM image and analysis of a top of the sample nitrided with the process 2 and tested at a maximum stress of 800MPa.

Figure 13 shows FIB-SEM images of the specimen that was nitrided with the process 2 and fatigued at 650MPa. Similar to the specimen tested at 800MPa, the longitudinal fatigue cracks originated at the surface and then propagated down through the compound and nitrided layers into the base material. Few secondary cracks were observed to initiate and propagate between the diffusion layer and the base material while other cracks continued to grow into the base material.

FIGURE 13 SEM and FIB milled cross sections of the fatigued surface and cracks of Ti64 specimen nitrided with the process 2 and tested at a maximum stress of 650 MPa.

Based on the EDS mapping of the left crack shown in Figure 13, it was found that a slightly higher concentration of titanium is detected in the compound and diffusion layers. The zone below the top layer is aluminium deficient. Nitrogen appears to be somewhat more concentrated in the upper segment of the cross-sectional area. Vanadium is detected at a higher concentration in the β -phase adjacent to the crack edge.

The results indicate that surface integrity and roughness together with deformation in the base alloy caused by fatigue lead to cracking of the nitrided layers. The cleavage facets and microcracks that were observed in the surrounding area of the nitrided layers can also grow from brittle phases such as compound layer and individual α -Ti grains that are less ductile than β -grains. It has been reported in [24, 25] that oxygen rich α -case can form in titanium alloys at high temperatures as nitrogen is an α -stabilising element that decreases β to α transformation [14]. α -case is a brittle phase with low damage tolerance, which contributes to brittle fracture [26]. Oxygen has been detected after the nitrided process 1, however, additional analysis is needed to confirm it. In addition, elements segregation and crystallographic orientations of different phases can have a strong effect on the layer properties as reported in [9] for plasma nitriding where the nitrided layers with higher microhardness experienced lower fatigue life. This was explained by brittleness of δ -TiN phase. The Al-rich thin layer, that was observed at the surface (Figure 12), probably contains brittle aluminium nitride compounds as shown in [10, 27, 28], which can also reduce fatigue life. Further characterisation work of the nitrided layers is on-going to understand their microstructural changes as well as effect of nitriding on surface roughness and fatigue performance. In addition, computation and simulation methods are being considered to understand atomic scale control of mechanical properties in the nitrided alloy.

CONCLUSIONS

The present study was performed on Ti64 Grade 5 alloy subjected to two nitrided processes and high cycle fatigue focusing on the crack initiation. Different characterisation techniques were used to understand connection between the nitrided alloys and fatigue performance. The following conclusions are as follows:

1. Both nitriding processes and specifically the formation of compound and diffusion layers, were found to be detrimental to the fatigue life of Ti64 alloy compared to untreated and extruded Ti64.
2. Fractographic analysis showed that fatigue cracks initiated from the surface in all specimens subjected to both nitriding processes, which indicates that surface condition (machining marks, roughness) can have a critical role in fatigue initiation. Both nitriding processes increased the surface roughness of the alloy, which could have decreased the critical stress for fracture (cracking).
3. The crack depths of the nitrided process 1 are shallower compared to the nitrided process 2 where the cracks penetrated the base materials and continued to grow.
4. Facets with smoother surface than the surrounding areas were observed on the fracture surfaces. Transgranular brittle fractures were seen within the nitrided layers while signs of cleavage were detected at the diffusion layers between the compound layer and the base material.
5. Grain coarsening of the individual α -Ti grains and the formation of brittle titanium and aluminium nitrides during nitriding could have affected the fatigue performance as they can act as stress concentration sites causing early crack initiation and faster crack propagation.

6. The mechanical properties of the nitrided layers, i.e. hardness, toughness and ductility, can also affect the resistance to cracking as the nitrided layers experienced cracking as a result of deformation in the underlying alloy caused by fatigue damage.
7. Residual stresses appear to have no influence on crack initiation due to their low magnitudes.

The results obtained in this study show that in order to improve surface properties while preserving fatigue life in nitrided Ti64 Grade 5 alloy it is necessary to decrease surface roughness after machining as well as during nitriding process. Additionally, better control of nitriding heat treatments to avoid grain growth and embrittlement of nitrided layers is also essential.

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